

Hydrolysate Production from Oil Palm Empty Fruit Bunch (EFB): Field-Scale Bucket Testing of Hot-Water Oil Stripping, Alkaline Hydrolysis and Enzymatic Saccharification

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Article 2 of a series on the characterisation and valorisation of oil palm empty fruit bunch

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Abstract

Oil palm empty fruit bunch (EFB) is a high-volume lignocellulosic residue of the palm oil industry whose basic physical and chemical properties were established in the first article of this series. Building on that baseline, this article reports field-scale ("bucket") testing of a multi-stage process to convert EFB fibre into a soluble hydrolysate: hot-water oil stripping, alkaline (sodium hydroxide) hydrolysis, water washing, and enzymatic saccharification, followed by filtration and concentration. Testing was performed on ~1 kg samples of fresh EFB collected at a working mill in West Kalimantan, Indonesia, and progress was tracked as chemical oxygen demand (COD). Hot-water stripping at 100 C released soluble COD up to ~23,000 mg/L; combining hot-water stripping with 1.0 % NaOH in a single stage gave ~43,500 mg/L (CODt). Alkaline-stage soluble COD rose with hydroxide concentration, from 10,780 mg/L at 0.5 % to 30,800 mg/L at 2.0 % NaOH. After enzymatic hydrolysis (cellulase, 50 C, 72 h, COD-corrected for the acetic acid used in pH adjustment), the cellulose-to-glucose conversion yield reached a maximum of 16.3 % at 2.0 % NaOH; the yields were re-derived independently from the raw COD data and confirmed. Severity-factor analysis ($\log R_0 = 1.3-1.8$) shows the process operated at low pre-treatment severity, which accounts for the modest sugar yield relative to literature routes using high-severity (~200 C) hydrothermal pre-treatment. The cost-benefit of the process - the balance between the recoverable COD or sugar and the energy, chemical and capital cost required to obtain it - is the subject of a subsequent article in this series.

1. Introduction

The first article in this series characterised EFB and established the baseline properties relevant to its conversion, including a measured dry-solids content of 56.08 % (moisture 43.92 %) and a compiled biochemical composition in which cellulose typically accounts for 43-45 % of the dry solids [1]. That cellulose fraction is the basis of EFB's potential as a feedstock for fermentable sugars, and the soluble organic matter liberated during processing is, in parallel, a substrate for anaerobic digestion to biogas. This article does not repeat the EFB description given in [1]; it takes those properties as given and examines what can be recovered from the fibre.

EFB hydrolysate is the product of the physico-chemical conversion of the cellulose-lignin fibre into cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin and sugars. While the chemistry has been demonstrated at bench scale with ~50 g samples, field testing at kilogram scale, using fresh feedstock taken directly from a mill, is necessary to demonstrate the practical behaviour of the material, to quantify the chemical and enzyme

demand, and to preserve sufficient significant figures when a design is scaled by a factor of a thousand from kilograms to tonnes. The work reported here was carried out for those reasons.

Throughout, process progress is measured as chemical oxygen demand (COD), which provides a single, inexpensive field measurement that tracks both the soluble organic load available for digestion and, after conversion using the glucose-COD equivalence, the fermentable-sugar yield.

2. The OPEFB Hydrolysate Process

The hydrolysate process is multi-stage, consisting of physical shredding, chemical hydrolysis (alkaline and, optionally, acid), and enzymatic hydrolysis, followed by filtration and concentration:

Physical shredding mechanically tears the EFB stalks into smaller fibres, normally with an electrically driven hammer mill. **Hot-water oil stripping** removes residual oil and a first fraction of soluble organics. **Alkaline hydrolysis**, analogous to the kraft process, cooks the shredded fibre in sodium hydroxide solution; the resulting black liquor is rich in lignin and is itself suitable for biogas production. **Acid hydrolysis** may follow the alkaline stage but was not performed in this study. **Enzymatic hydrolysis** digests the pre-treated fibre in off-the-shelf cellulase enzyme solutions of the type used in the biofuels industry, typically at 50 C for 24-72 h. Finally the liquid hydrolysate is drained, filtered and concentrated; the residual fibre, mainly lignin, can be composted.

The resulting sugar solution can be concentrated into a higher-grade sugar syrup or fermented to bioethanol, while the various COD-rich liquors (brown, black and white) can be fed to an anaerobic digester.

3. Severity Factor

The severity factor R_0 quantifies the combined intensity of a thermal pre-treatment as a single number, combining temperature and time:

$$\log R_0 = \log[t \times \exp((T - 100) / 14.75)]$$

where T is the temperature in degrees Celsius and t the time in minutes. It is widely used to compare pre-treatments of lignocellulosic feedstocks. For the conditions used here - hot-water and alkaline stages at 85-100 C for about 60 minutes - the severity is low, $\log R_0 = 1.3$ (85 C) to 1.8 (100 C). For context, hydrothermal routes operating near 200 C for 10-20 minutes correspond to $\log R_0 = 3.9-4.3$, two to three orders of magnitude more severe. This difference is central to interpreting the sugar yields reported below.

4. Materials and Methods

4.1 Sample collection and preparation

On 25 January 2024, fresh oil palm empty fruit bunches were collected from a palm oil mill in West Kalimantan, Indonesia. Using hand shears the frondlets were cut from the coir-like pith and reduced to

~1 cm lengths, at which point the individual fibres separated readily, giving sample charges of approximately 1 kg (Figure 1).

Figure 1. EFB frondlet.

4.2 Test regime

Five samples were processed under the regime summarised in Table 1. Sample 1 was reserved for dry-solids determination (reported in [1]); Samples 2-5 were taken through oil stripping, alkaline hydrolysis and, for Samples 3-5, enzymatic hydrolysis, with NaOH concentration and enzyme time varied.

Sample	Description of test	Hot-water temp.	NaOH conc.	Enzyme time
1	Dry solids determination	N/A	N/A	N/A
2	Oil stripping, alkaline hydrolysis	85-45 C	0.5 %	N/A
3	Combined oil stripping & alkaline, enzyme	85-45 C	1.0 %	24 h
4	Oil stripping, alkaline, enzyme	100 C	1.0 %	72 h
5	Oil stripping, alkaline, enzyme	100 C	2.0 %	72 h

Table 1. Sample test matrix.

4.3 Oil stripping

Each ~1 kg chopped sample was placed in a stainless-steel vessel with 3.7 L of clean water. For one sample the water was added hot (80 C) and allowed to cool over one hour; for the others the mixture was boiled for one hour (Figure 2). The fibre was then drained and weighed, and the liquid - termed brown liquor for its colour - retained for COD analysis.

Figure 2. Hot-water oil-stripping stage: EFB fibre boiled in water to release residual oil and soluble organics, producing the brown liquor.

4.4 Alkaline hydrolysis

The oil-stripped fibre was treated with 3.7 L of sodium hydroxide solution at 0.5 %, 1.0 % or 2.0 % w/w, brought to the boil and held for one hour. The liquid (black liquor) was drained, its pH measured with a calibrated handheld meter, and a sample retained for COD.

4.5 Washing

The drained fibre was returned to the vessel with 3.0 L of clean water, stirred for two minutes and drained. The liquid (white liquor) had its pH measured and a sample retained for COD; its COD and pH indicate residual black liquor being rinsed from within the porous fibre.

4.6 Enzymatic hydrolysis

Washed fibre (Samples 3-5) was transferred to a bucket and made up with clean water to 8 % dry-solids loading. The pH was adjusted to 5.0 with small, measured additions of 25 % glacial acetic acid - the only mild acid safely available in the field. Cellulase enzyme (liquid cellulase, or a powdered cellulase / laccase / xylanase blend; Advanced Enzymes Ltd., India, and Sunson Industry Group, China; Figure 3) was added and the mixture held at 50 C for 24-72 h with occasional stirring. Sugar development was monitored by periodic refractometer (Brix) readings. At the end of the run the liquid was drained, the fibre squeezed to simulate a belt press, and a final COD sample taken; this liquid is the EFB hydrolysate.

Figure 3. Commercial cellulase enzyme of the type used for the enzymatic hydrolysis stage.

4.7 COD testing

Chemical oxygen demand was determined by PT. Ecodey Agro Energi, Depok, Indonesia. Oil-stripping liquors, being oily and effectively unfilterable, were measured as total COD (COD_t); all other samples were filtered through a 0.45 µm filter and measured as soluble COD (COD_s). The liquors recovered from successive stages (Figure 4) range from the pale brown of the oil-stripping liquor to the dark black liquor of the alkaline stage.

Figure 4. Liquor samples collected for COD analysis, showing the progression from pale oil-stripping (brown) liquor to the dark alkaline-stage (black) liquor.

4.8 Sugar-yield calculation

Sugar yield was derived from COD using the glucose equivalence that a 1000 mg/L glucose solution exerts a COD of 1067 mg/L; dividing a measured COD by 1.067 gives the equivalent glucose concentration. Total glucose was obtained by multiplying this concentration by the total water in the sample (added water plus water held within the fibre). The cellulose available was taken as the dry-solids mass multiplied by an assumed cellulose fraction of 44 % [1]. Yield is the ratio of glucose produced

to cellulose available, expressed as a percentage. Where acetic acid had been added for pH control, its COD contribution was measured separately and subtracted before the yield was computed.

5. Results

5.1 Hot-water oil stripping

Hot-water stripping released substantial soluble organics, increasing with temperature (Table 2). At 100 C the brown liquor reached 23,000 mg/L (CODt).

Sample	Temperature (C)	CODt (mg/L)
2	85-45	14,490
4	100	19,400
5	100	23,000

Table 2. Hot-water oil-stripping COD (total).

5.2 Combined oil stripping and alkaline hydrolysis

Performing hot-water stripping and 1.0 % alkaline hydrolysis together in a single stage (Sample 3) gave a total COD of 43,500 mg/L (Table 3) - approximately the sum of the COD of the two stages run separately, indicating the two contributions are largely additive.

Sample	Temperature (C)	NaOH (%)	CODt (mg/L)
3	85-45	1.0	43,500

Table 3. Combined oil-stripping and alkaline-hydrolysis COD (total).

5.3 Alkaline hydrolysis

In the dedicated alkaline stage, soluble COD increased monotonically with hydroxide concentration, roughly tripling between 0.5 % and 2.0 % NaOH (Table 4). This is consistent with progressive delignification and solubilisation of the fibre at higher alkali loading.

Sample	Temperature (C)	NaOH (% w/w)	CODs (mg/L)
2	80-40	0.5	10,780
4	100	1.0	22,600
5	100	2.0	30,800

Table 4. Alkaline-hydrolysis soluble COD versus hydroxide concentration.

5.4 Washing

The wash water (Sample 5) carried a soluble COD of 7,000 mg/L at pH 11.3, confirming that black liquor continues to be rinsed from within the porous fibre after draining and that a wash stage recovers additional soluble organics.

5.5 Enzymatic hydrolysis and sugar yield

Because acetic acid was used for pH adjustment, its COD contribution was quantified (Table 5) and subtracted from the measured enzyme-stage COD before the yield calculation.

Sample	Acetic acid (mL, 25%)	COD of acetic acid (mg)	Water (L)	Acetic COD (mg/L)
3	17.5	4,892	5.56	880
4	37.5	10,483	7.50	1,397
5	36	10,064	6.52	1,543

Table 5. Acetic-acid COD correction applied to the enzyme stage.

The enzyme-stage results, after correction, are given in Table 6. The cellulose-to-glucose conversion yield increased with alkali pre-treatment severity, reaching a maximum of 16.3 % for Sample 5 (2.0 % NaOH, 72 h).

Sample	Brix (%)	CODs measured (mg/L)	CODs adjusted (mg/L)	Yield (%)
3	0.7	7,050	6,170	13.9
4	0.5	6,400	5,003	14.9
5	0.8	7,170	5,627	16.3

Table 6. Enzyme-hydrolysis soluble COD (acetic-acid corrected) and cellulose-to-glucose yield.

To verify these yields they were re-derived independently from the adjusted COD values (Table 7). Converting each adjusted COD to a glucose-equivalent concentration and multiplying by the sample water volume gives 32-35 g of glucose per ~1 kg charge; dividing by the cellulose available (44 % of the dry-solids mass) reproduces the reported yields of 13.9-16.3 %, confirming the calculation.

Sample	Adjusted CODs (mg/L)	Glucose conc. (mg/L)	Water (L)	Total glucose (g)
3	6,170	5,783	5.56	32.2
4	5,003	4,689	7.50	35.2
5	5,627	5,274	6.52	34.4

Table 7. Independent re-derivation of glucose mass from adjusted COD (glucose = COD / 1.067).

5.6 Filtration and concentration

Filtration of the Sample 5 hydrolysate through 25 um paper reduced soluble COD from 3,990 to 2,142 mg/L after acetic-acid correction. The removal of fine solids - and the lower COD of the filtrate sample held before testing - indicates that enzymatic hydrolysis continues on the micro-fibre particles in suspension while the sample awaits analysis, implying that extending the hydrolysis time would increase the overall yield. On concentration (simulating nanofiltration), an 87 % reduction in volume raised the soluble COD to 30,500 mg/L, demonstrating that the dilute hydrolysate can be concentrated into a high-COD, high-sugar liquor.

6. Comparison with the Literature

Akita, Yusoff and Fujimoto [2] prepared OPEFB hydrolysate using high-severity hydrothermal pre-treatment at 200 C followed by enzymatic hydrolysis, obtaining a glucose yield of 234 mg per gram of OPEFB at 61.7 % of the theoretical maximum. The contrast with the present work is instructive. Their hydrothermal step corresponds to $\log R_0 = 3.9-4.3$, against 1.3-1.8 for the mild hot-water and alkaline conditions used here. The much lower severity of a field-deployable, atmospheric-pressure process is the principal reason our cellulose-to-glucose conversion reached only 16.3 %. The practical trade-off is between yield and capital/operational simplicity: high-severity routes need pressurised hydrothermal reactors, while the alkaline route demonstrated here can be operated with mill steam and simple vessels, producing both a modest sugar stream and a large COD-rich liquor for digestion.

7. Discussion

Two products emerge from the same process. The first is soluble COD: hot-water stripping alone reached ~23,000 mg/L and a combined stripping/alkaline stage ~43,500 mg/L, with the alkaline COD scaling with hydroxide dose. This soluble fraction is readily digestible and represents recoverable energy that can be fed to existing anaerobic digesters alongside palm oil mill effluent, increasing biogas yield without additional fresh feedstock. The second is fermentable sugar, recovered at a modest 16.3 % cellulose-to-glucose conversion under the mild conditions tested.

Two observations point to straightforward yield improvements. First, soluble COD - and therefore solubilised, hydrolysable material - rose steadily with alkali concentration up to 2.0 % NaOH, so the optimum hydroxide loading had not been reached. Second, the evidence that hydrolysis continued in the sample bottle indicates that the 72 h enzymatic step was not run to completion; a longer residence time would raise yield. Both levers, together with the addition of the acid-hydrolysis stage omitted here, are candidates for additional research. Each, however, carries a cost in energy, chemicals or reactor size, so whether higher intensity is worthwhile is a question of cost-benefit rather than of yield alone.

What the field testing establishes is that the process behaves predictably at kilogram scale on fresh mill feedstock, that COD is a workable single-parameter tracking measurement, and that both a sugar stream and a substantial COD stream are recoverable from EFB using equipment compatible with a working mill.

8. Conclusion

Field-scale bucket testing of fresh EFB confirmed that a multi-stage hot-water, alkaline and enzymatic process produces a soluble hydrolysate. Hot-water oil stripping released soluble COD up to ~23,000 mg/L; a combined stripping/alkaline stage reached ~43,500 mg/L; and alkaline-stage soluble COD rose with hydroxide concentration to 30,800 mg/L at 2.0 % NaOH. After COD correction for the acetic acid used in pH adjustment, the cellulose-to-glucose conversion yield reached 16.3 %, a value independently re-derived from the raw COD data. Severity-factor analysis ($\log R_0 = 1.3-1.8$) shows the process ran at low pre-treatment severity, which explains the modest sugar yield relative to high-severity hydrothermal routes, while the recoverable soluble COD remains a substantial, digestible energy

stream. Both a fermentable-sugar product and a digestible COD stream are therefore recoverable from EFB using equipment compatible with a working mill, and higher yields are attainable in principle through higher alkali loading, longer enzymatic residence or an added acid stage. Whether any of these is economic depends on the balance of the recovered value against the energy, chemical and capital cost required.

Author Contributions

D.S.: conceptualisation, methodology, validation, investigation, writing - original draft. A.B.: review and editing.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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